

Research

Comparison Of Intrathecal Morphine Versus Fentanyl Added to Hyperbaric Bupivacaine for Lower Limb Surgeries

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Abstract: Background: Spinal anesthesia with bupivacaine is administered routinely for lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. Intrathecal opioids are synergistic with local anesthetics and intensify the sensory block without increasing the sympathetic block. They also increase postoperative analgesia of bupivacaine in SAB. This study compared the efficacy in terms of onset of sensory and motor block and time to first rescue analgesia of intrathecal fentanyl with intrathecal morphine added to hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb surgeries. Methodology: A prospective, single blinded, randomized controlled trial was performed. Fifty-eight patients undergoing lower limb surgeries under spinal anesthesia received 20 mcg (0.4 ml) of fentanyl with 3 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (n = 29) in group F versus 200 mcg (0.2 ml) of morphine with 3 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (n = 29) in group M, total volume of 3.4 ml in both the groups. Hemodynamic variables: heart rate, mean arterial pressure and SPO₂ were recorded immediately after injection of the drug and every 5 min for first 15 min, then every 15 min throughout the duration of surgery. Time of onset of maximum sensory level and complete motor block were noted. Time to first rescue analgesia was recorded and analyzed using appropriate statistical tests. Results: The time to reach maximum sensory level was shorter in group F (9.86±0.78) min compared to group M (11.48±1.12) min (P <0.05) which was statistically significant. Time of onset of complete motor block was shorter in group F (6.03±0.90) minutes compared to group M (6.82±0.75) minutes (P <0.05) which was statistically significant. Time to first rescue analgesia was longer in group M (534.90±50.49) minutes compared to group F (343.03±38.53) minutes (P<0.05). Conclusions: The time to reach maximum sensory level and time of onset of complete motor block were shorter with intrathecal fentanyl than with intrathecal morphine. Duration of post-operative pain relief with intrathecal morphine added to hyperbaric bupivacaine is longer than with intrathecal fentanyl added to hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb surgeries.

Keywords: Fentanyl, Hyperbaric bupivacaine, Lower limb surgeries, Morphine, Subarachnoid block

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Introduction

Spinal anesthesia with bupivacaine is administered routinely for lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. The resulting nerve block is sufficient to ensure patient's wellbeing, while motor block facilitates the surgeon's work. It also provides effective pain relief in the initial post-operative period.[1] The unmatched reliability and simplicity of subarachnoid block has made spinal anesthesia a very useful and successful technique in managing all surgical cases undergoing infra umbilical procedures. It is safe, easy to perform, effective, inexpensive with low failure rate and minimal systemic local anesthetic toxicity. It inhibits the stress response to surgery, blunts the autonomic and somatic responses to pain, and facilitates breathing, coughing and early ambulation. The main limitations of spinal anesthesia are its relative short duration of action and lack of desired prolonged postoperative analgesia when performed only with local anesthetics. For prolongation of anesthetic and analgesic effect, the increased dose of bupivacaine needed can cause hemodynamic compromise due to high and dense sympathetic block.[2] Neuraxial adjuvants include opioids (fentanyl, sufentanil, morphine), sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃), vasoconstrictors, alpha-2 adrenoceptor agonists, cholinergic agonists, N-methyl-d-aspartate (NMDA) antagonists and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptor agonists.[3] Fentanyl has no active metabolites and is approximately 800 times more lipid soluble than morphine. There is limited cephalad spread with segmental analgesia and a lower incidence of pruritus.[4] In our institute, subarachnoid block is one of the common modes of anesthesia technique. We commonly use intrathecal morphine and fentanyl as adjuncts to enhance the effect of hyperbaric bupivacaine in subarachnoid block. As such study has not been done in our institute before, I felt the need to examine the efficacy of intrathecal morphine as compared to that of intrathecal fentanyl.

Research Methodology

General objective: To compare the quality of anesthesia and postoperative pain relief of intrathecal morphine versus fentanyl with hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb surgeries.

Specific objectives: To assess time for onset of maximum sensory height. To assess time for onset of complete motor block (Bromage 3). To compare the intra-operative hemodynamic (MAP, HR). To determine the time of first dose of rescue analgesia in the post-operative period.

Type of study: Comparative, prospective, randomized, single blind, interventional study.

Study place: Bir Hospital and National Trauma Center, NAMS, Kathmandu.

Duration of study: March 2017 to December 2017

Using the following formula for estimating sample size:

$$n = \{2(Z\alpha + Z\beta)^2 \times SD^2\} / d^2$$

Where n = the number of patients in each group,

$Z\alpha$ = constant at given alpha error,

$Z\beta$ = constant at given beta error,

SD = standard deviation,

d = difference between two means, or effect size.

Using following formula for the derivation of pooled standard deviation (SD)

$$SD^2 = [(n_1-1) s_1^2 + (n_2-1) s_2^2] / (n_1 + n_2 - 2)$$

As per the study done by Goma HM et al [8], using onset of motor block (mean \pm SD) as the Primary Outcome Variable. Fentanyl: (onset of complete motor block: 5.57 \pm 0.23) and nalbuphine: (onset of complete motor block: 5.72 \pm 0.17). The difference between two means (d) was 0.15. The number of patients in each group was 30.

$$SD^2 = [(30-1) (0.23)^2 + (30-1) (0.17)^2] / (30+30-2)$$

$$SD^2 = 0.0409$$

Using the derived data into the before mentioned formula with the power of 80% ($Z\beta = 0.84$) and at significance level of 95% ($Z\alpha = 1.96$) the required sample size calculation will be as follows.

$$n = \{2(Z\alpha + Z\beta)^2 \times SD^2\} / d^2$$

$$n = \{2 (1.96 + 0.84)^2 \times 0.0409\} / (0.15)^2$$

$$n = 28.5$$

Hence, at least 29 patients should be enrolled in each group. Therefore, total number of patients enrolled in this study was 58.

Inclusion criteria

- ASA PS I & II
- 18-60 years of age
- Both gender
- Patients scheduled to undergo lower limb surgeries

Exclusion criteria

- Patient's refusal
- Contraindications of spinal anesthesia
- Allergic to bupivacaine or opiates
- Patient requiring intra operative analgesia
- Patient who is unable to sit

After obtaining approval from institutional review board (IRB) of NAMS, Bir Hospital, 58 adult patients undergoing elective surgery under subarachnoid block, meeting the inclusion criteria and not having any of the exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. ASA PS I and II include normal healthy patients and patients with mild systemic disease respectively. All the patients were admitted to the hospital at least a day prior to surgery. Patients were informed in detail about the nature of the study during pre-anesthetic checkup visit and an informed written consent was taken from patients or their guardians. Demographic details of the patient were recorded and a thorough pre-anesthetic history, physical and biochemical examination were carried out and noted. During the pre-anesthetic checkup, all the patients were shown a numeric pain rating scale and were taught in detail about how to use a 10-cm numeric pain rating scale with 0-cm representing no pain and 10-cm the worst possible pain. Pain scale reading from 1 to 3 was considered as mild pain. Pain scale reading from 4 to 6 was considered as moderate pain. Pain scale reading from 7 to 10 was considered as severe pain.

Figure 1: Numeric Pain Rating Scale

On the day of surgery, drugs were prepared. Patients were divided into two groups, group M received 200 mcg (0.2 ml) of morphine as an adjunct plus 0.2 ml of NS and group F received 20 mcg (0.4 ml) of fentanyl as an adjunct to 3ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine. The total volume used in both groups was 3.4 ml. The patients enrolled into the study were randomly allocated to one of the two study groups M or F named according to the drug to be administered. Lottery method was used for randomization, where total 58 small pieces of papers, out of which equal number ($n=29$ each) of papers with code name either M or F written on it, were kept inside a container. Anesthesia assistant was asked to pick up one paper from the container and then assignment to the respective group as per written on it was done. When the patient arrived in the operation theatre, standard monitors: NIBP, pulse oximeter and ECG were attached. Baseline

values of heart rate, mean arterial pressure, SPO2 were recorded. Intravenous line was opened with 18G cannula. Pre-loading was done with 10ml/kg of NS over 10-15 minutes. Patient was kept in sitting position and then sterile painting and draping of the injection site was done. Subarachnoid block was performed under all aseptic conditions, in sitting position, midline approach, L3-L4 or L4-L5 space by using 27-gauge Whitacre spinal needle. Before inserting the needle, field block was obtained by 2ml of 2% plain lignocaine. After 1 minute, introducer was inserted and SAB was done. Drug was injected after free flow of CSF. Patient was immediately kept in supine position. Hemodynamic variables: heart rate, mean arterial pressure and SPO2 were recorded immediately after injection of the drug and every 5 min for first 15 min, then every 15 min throughout the duration of surgery. Level of sensory block was checked by pin prick method by using hypodermic 23G needle at mid clavicular line on both sides. Maximum sensory level reached and the time to reach maximum sensory level was noted. Motor block was assessed by using bromage scale.

- 0= No paralysis
- 1= Inability to raise extended leg
- 2=Inability to flex the knee
- 3=Inability to flex the ankle (complete motor block)

Time of onset of complete motor block (inability to flex the ankle) was noted. Painting and draping by the surgeon were allowed once the T10 sensory level was reached. Hypotension was defined as a decrease in mean arterial pressure by 20% from the baseline or mean arterial pressure of less than 60 mm Hg and was treated with intravenous bolus of crystalloids and 6 mg of inj. mephentermine. Bradycardia was defined as heart rate less than 60 beats per min and/or less than 20% of baseline value and was treated with 0.6mg of inj. atropine.

If SPO2 dropped below 90%, supplemental oxygen was given via facemask. If the block failed or height of sensory level was not achieved within 15 minutes, general anesthesia was given and the patient was excluded from the study. Time to first rescue analgesia (from the time of subarachnoid injection to Numeric Pain Rating Scale of 4 or more, or when the patient complains of pain) was recorded. Pethidine, promethazine (1mg/kg, 0.5mg/kg respectively) were given intramuscularly (IM) as rescue analgesia. Numeric pain rating scale was used to assess the pain in the PACU every half hourly till the score became 4. Data collection was done by filling the proforma containing the demographic details of the patient (age, gender, ASA and duration of surgery). Hemodynamic variables: heart rate (HR) and mean arterial blood pressure (MAP) were recorded (as per the methodology) in the proforma. Time to achieve highest sensory level and time of onset of complete motor block (grade 3) were recorded. Any adverse events were noted and treated as per the hospital protocol. Data entry and statistical analysis were performed using statistical software such as SPSS. Data analysis was done using suitable tests. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or numbers (percentages). Result was considered statistically significant if p value < 0.05. Chi-square test was used for categorical data (Gender, ASA grade). Unpaired t- test was used for comparisons between the two groups.

Results

Demographic data of the patient

Age Distribution:

The age distributions of the patients included in this study were comparable in two groups. The mean age of patients in fentanyl group (group F) was 41.93 \pm 11.54 years; in morphine group (group M) it was 38.10 \pm 11.58 years. There was no statistically significant difference in the mean age of patients between the two groups (p-value: 0.212).

Table 1: Age of the patients in the two groups (Mean \pm SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Age (yrs)	41.93 \pm 11.54	38.10 \pm 11.58	0.2126

Figure 2: Age distribution between two groups

Weight distribution:

The weight distributions of the patients included in this study were comparable in two groups. The mean weight of patients in Fentanyl group (group F) was 60.00±6.79 kg; in Morphine group (group M) it was 62.86±8.60 kg. There was no statistically significant difference in mean age between the two groups (p-value: 0.165).

Table 2: Weight of the patients in the two groups (Mean ± SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Weight (kg)	60.00±6.79	62.86±8.60	0.165

Figure 3: Weight distribution between two groups

Duration of surgery:

The mean duration of surgery was longer in fentanyl group (Group F) than in morphine (Group M). The mean duration of surgery in fentanyl group (Group F) was 94.68±19.72min, in morphine group (Group M) it was 83.44±19.80 min. There was statistically significant difference in mean duration of surgery between the two groups (p-value: 0.035).

Table 3: Duration of surgery in the two groups (Mean ± SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Duration of surgery(min)	94.68±19.72	83.44±19.80	0.035

Figure 4: Duration of surgery in two groups

ASA Physical status:

The ASA physical status of patients in both groups was comparable. Twenty-six patients in Group F and twenty-five patients in Group M were of ASA physical status I, three patients in Group F and four patients in Group M were of ASA physical status II, these data were not statistically significant (p-value: 1). There was no statistically significant difference between ASA physical status between the groups.

Table 4: ASA Physical status of patients in the two groups

ASA PS	Group F (n=29)	Group M (n=29)
ASA PS I	26	25
ASA PS II	3	4

Figure 5: ASA physical status

Gender:

The gender of patients in both groups was comparable. Twenty-five patients in Group F and twenty patients in Group M were of male gender, four patients in group F and nine patients in Group M were of female gender. There was no statistically significant difference between these data (p-value: 0.115). There was no significant difference between gender between the groups.

Table 5: Sex distribution in the two groups

Gender	Group F (n=29)	Group M (n=29)
Male	25	20
Female	4	9

Figure 6: Sex distribution in two groups

Adverse effects:

Out of 58 patients, no side effects were observed in all 29 (100%) patients in group F and in 27 (93.1%) patients in Group M. The difference was not statistically significant (p value: 0.472). Two patients had pruritus in group M. There was no incidence of nausea/vomiting and desaturation in both the groups.

Table 6: Incidence of adverse effects (number of cases)

Variables	Group F	Group M
Pruritus	0	2
Nausea/Vomiting	0	0
Desaturation	0	0

Time to reach maximum sensory block:

The time to reach maximum sensory block was shorter in fentanyl group (Group F) than in morphine (Group M). The mean time of onset of sensory block in Fentanyl group (Group F) was 9.86±0.79 min, in Morphine group (Group M) it was 11.48±1.12 min. There was statistically significant difference in mean time to reach maximum sensory block between the two groups (p-value: 0.000).

Table 7: Time for onset of highest sensory level (Mean ± SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Time for onset of highest sensory level(min)	9.86±0.79	11.48±1.12	0.000

Figure 7: Time to achieve maximum sensory block

Time for onset of complete motor block

The time for onset of complete motor block was shorter in fentanyl group (Group F) than in morphine group (Group M). The mean time for onset of complete motor block in Fentanyl group (Group F) was 6.03±0.91 min, in morphine group (Group M) it was 6.83±0.76 min. There was statistically significant difference in mean time for onset of complete block between the two groups (p-value: 0.001).

Table 8: Time for onset of complete motor block (Mean ± SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Time for onset of complete motor block(min)	6.03±0.91	6.83±0.76	0.0006

Figure 8: Time for onset of complete motor block

Time of first rescue analgesia

The time of first rescue analgesia was longer in morphine group (Group M) as compared to fentanyl group (Group F). The mean time of first rescue analgesia in morphine group (Group M) was 534.90±50.50 min, in Fentanyl group (Group F) it was 343.03±38.53 min. There was statistically significant difference in mean time of first rescue analgesia between the two groups (p-value: 0.000).

Table 9: Time of first rescue analgesia (Mean ± SD)

Characteristic	Group F	Group M	P value
Time of first rescue analgesia (min)	343.03±38.53	534.90±50.50	0.000

Figure 9: Time of first rescue analgesia

Hemodynamic parameters

The mean baseline heart rate, 81.79±13.56 beats/minute in Group F and 80.90±11.20 beats/minute in Group M were comparable to each other (p-value: 0.784). There was no statistically significant difference in heart rate between the two groups except at 105 minutes after SAB (p-value: 0.045).

The mean baseline MAP, 91.10±16.74 mm of Hg in Group F and 85.44±11.89 mm of Hg in Group M were comparable to each other (p-value: 0.144). There was no statistically significant difference in MAP between the two groups.

Table 10: Heart rate (HR) at different time in two groups (Mean ± SD)

Heart rate (bpm)	Group F (n=29)	Group M (n=29)	p-value
Baseline	81.79±13.56	80.89±11.20	0.785
5 min	82.65±13.11	81.89±10.98	0.812
10 min	82.68±14.78	81.86±11.93	0.815
15 min	82.62±14.91	80.34±11.59	0.519
30 min	81.86±16.26	80.58±12.96	0.742
45 min	81.37±15.06	78.10±13.14	0.387
60 min	80.65±14.22	76.30±12.84	0.242
75 min	82.20±14.00	75.28±11.13	0.076
90 min	81.70±14.33	77.23±11.53	0.354
105 min	86.55±11.08	74.00±7.58	0.045
120 min	88.80±15.02	83.00±4.24	0.631

Figure 10: Mean heart rate (HR) at different time intervals in two groups

Table 11: MAP at different time in two groups (Mean ± SD)

MAP (mm of Hg)	Group F (n=29)	Group M (n=29)	p-value
Baseline	91.10±16.74	85.44±11.89	0.144
5 min	83.93±15.35	79.79±11.36	0.249
10 min	82.17±15.22	77.51±11.78	0.198
15 min	80.34±13.37	76.41±10.83	0.224
30 min	78.79±12.00	76.72±12.56	0.524
45 min	83.27±14.10	78.46±10.77	0.155
60 min	83.34±12.08	80.11±10.81	0.303
75 min	84.12±12.51	79.23±11.53	0.182
90 min	84.85±13.24	80.15±11.45	0.303
105 min	88.54±13.86	76.20±8.67	0.091
120 min	91.20±18.70	71.00±1.41	0.208

Figure 11: Mean MAP at different time intervals in two groups

Discussion

The patients studied between the groups were similar in age, weight, ASA status which were statistically insignificant. Duration of surgery was longer in group F as compared to group M and was statistically significant.

In our study, the mean time to achieve the maximum sensory block level was 9.86 ± 0.79 min in group F and 11.48 ± 1.12 min in group M. (p-value: 0.000). It showed that there was statistically significant difference in the time to achieve the maximum sensory block height which was shorter in fentanyl group as compared to morphine group.

Similar to our study, Agrawal A et al [5] compared bupivacaine 12.5 mg (Group I), bupivacaine 12.5 mg + morphine 0.2 mg (Group II), bupivacaine 12.5 mg + fentanyl 25 mcg (Group III), preservative free physiological saline 0.9% was added to all the solutions to achieve a total volume of 4 ml in lower segment cesarean section. They found that the time to achieve maximum sensory block height was 4.64 ± 0.28 min in Group I, 4.50 ± 0.22 in Group II, and 4.30 ± 0.12 min in Group III. The onset of maximum sensory block was faster in fentanyl group as compared to morphine group and only bupivacaine group (p-value<0.05). Because of high volume (4ml) in study done by Agrawal et al[5] in case of cesarean section, onset of time for maximum sensory block was faster in both morphine and fentanyl group than in our study.

In our study, the mean time to achieve complete motor block (Bromage 3) in group F was 6.03 ± 0.91 min and in group M was 6.83 ± 0.76 min. The time for onset of complete motor block was shorter in group F as compared to group M (p-value: 0.001).

The mean baseline heart rate and MAP were comparable between the two groups. The mean baseline heart rate, 81.79 ± 13.56 beats/minute in Group F and 80.90 ± 11.20 beats/minute in Group M were comparable to each other with the p-value of 0.784. There was no statistically significant difference in heart rate between the two groups except at 105 minutes after SAB with the p-value of 0.045. The mean baseline MAP, 91.10 ± 16.74 mm of Hg in Group F and 85.44 ± 11.89 mm of Hg in Group M were comparable to each other with the p-value of 0.144. There was no statistically significant difference in MAP between the two groups.

Similar to our study, Kilickaya R et al[6] compared group F (n=25) that received 25 mcg fentanyl (0.5 ml) plus 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (2.5 ml) with group M that received 0.1mg of morphine (0.5 ml) plus 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (2.5 ml). There was no statistically significant difference between the groups in terms of systolic and diastolic blood pressure. There was also no statistically significant difference in the heart rate between the groups.

In our study, the mean time of first rescue analgesia in morphine group (Group M) was 534.90 ± 50.50 min, in fentanyl group (Group F) it was 343.03 ± 38.53 min. There was statistically significant difference in mean time of first rescue analgesia between the two groups (p-value: 0.000). The time of first rescue analgesia was longer in morphine group (Group M) as compared to fentanyl group (Group F).

Salmah GS et al[7] compared 0.1mg morphine with 25 mcg fentanyl added to 1.8 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia in caesarean section. Time to the first PCA morphine dose as rescue was at (297.4 ± 112.0) minutes in morphine group and (197.7 ± 60.0) minutes in fentanyl group. These results showed significant difference in time to first PCA morphine (p<0.05). This result is similar to our study. However, the time to first rescue analgesia in both the groups is shorter as compared to our study. This might be because of the higher dose of morphine and hyperbaric bupivacaine used in our study.

Out of 58 patients, no side effects were observed in all 29 (100%) patients in group F and in 27 (93.1%) patients in Group M. Two patients had pruritus in group M. There were no nausea/vomiting and desaturation in both the groups.

Thornton P et al[8] compared group 1 that received both intrathecal morphine 100 mcg and intrathecal fentanyl 10 mcg along with 2.3 ml of 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine with group 2 that received intrathecal preservative free morphine 100 µg with 2.3 ml 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine. All incidences of side effects such as nausea, vomiting and pruritus were higher in Group 1 than in Group 2, although only of significance in those with pruritus.

Conclusion

Use of intrathecal fentanyl enhances the time of onset of maximum sensory block height and complete motor block more than that of intrathecal morphine whereas intrathecal morphine prolongs the postoperative analgesic duration more than that of intrathecal fentanyl when added to hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb surgeries. However, they both have similar hemodynamic effects with minimal adverse effects.

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